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UNITY OF MORALITY AND AESTHETICS IN PERSONAL MIND: PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the philosophical analysis of the place of morality and aesthetics in the consciousness of the individual, their synthesis. The problems of the formation and development of the ideal in the consciousness of a person, structure, levels of moral and aesthetic consciousness of a person are analyzed. It was analyzed that in the spiritual existence of a person, morality and aesthetics are inseparable at the same time. Ethical consciousness, aesthetic activity are closely interconnected, the aspects related to the aesthetic approach to reality are analyzed.

Key words: spiritual existence of a person, ideal, morality, aesthetics. aesthetic consciousness, taste, personality, art, aesthetic feeling, taste, moral ideal, spirituality, aesthetic culture, truth, goodness, beauty,

INTRODUCTION

From the history of philosophical thought, we know that the trinity, such as truth, goodness and beauty, were perceived as valuable, objective aspects of a person's spiritual existence. According to a number of authors, although the perception of people, ideals and criteria of beauty, goodness and truth change, there will always be standards that generalize ideas, criteria and norms that regulate and generalize them. These standards are crystallized in the process of the development of human imagination, shaping the spiritual existence of a person on the basis of national and universal values. Indeed, three ideas that are the spiritual value of humanity have been a major topic of controversy, from the Avesta to the Koran, from ancient Greek philosophers to modern philosophy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

There are also researchers who have defined the unity of morality and aesthetics with the concept of "perixorez", which reflects the dialectical-antinomic relationship between truth, goodness and beauty - the traditional trinity. The results of these social relations, covering the spiritual culture of a person, in contrast to the original, are concentrated in the modern "inseparably indivisible" unity and are expressed through the moral essence, aesthetic meaning. In the spiritual existence of a person, the concept of morality and aesthetics as a single, two-sided, single foundation is gaining more and more importance. Instead of the concepts of "perixorez" and "unrelated", which are internal relations arising from the interaction of different views on the three ideas mentioned above, it seems appropriate to use the concept of "architecture" from the outside. The concept of perixorez has a philosophical basis for the trinity of truth, goodness and beauty. That is, the tragic-antinomy of a person's spiritual existence consists in the fact that the trinity of truth, goodness and beauty is in a

state of "disunity", and the combination of this trinity in ethical and aesthetic unity (inseparability) creates an ideal. existence in cultural architecture. At the same time, spiritual existence is closely related to the ideas of unity and non-coincidence of higher goals.

This state of incoherence, inseparability of twin concepts means that human knowledge is integrated into one system, trying to build its architecture, unstable situations arise in the systematization of knowledge. According to Kant, "human thought is inherently architectural. Since the architectural interest in contemplation includes a natural benevolence towards the theses of the dissertation "[1,], this human aspiration can be called a true philosophical aspiration.

In other words, the essence of inseparability lies, on the one hand, in the recognition of truth, goodness and beauty as the inseparability of culture in its current state, and, on the other hand, the ideal expresses its desire for inseparability in a cultural context. architecture. This metaphysical trinity of human spiritual unity plays the role of a certain norm of philosophical thinking, the essence of which is the perception and understanding of the ideal existence of the personality in philosophy, spiritual values in culture. This inner dialectical and antinomic relationship is therefore expressed by philosophers in terms of perichoresis or architectonics.

In the works of G.G. Shpet "Art is a form of cognition" and G.A. Zavalko "Philosophical Problems of Aesthetics" there are two different views on submission and disobedience to the threefold law of moral and aesthetic knowledge. These authors seek to "build a new edifice of free aesthetics" outside of morality and logic, that is, "to justify aesthetics as an independent fundamental science, independent of psychological, metaphysical and epistemological foundations." [2,297] For this, Shpet seeks to move away from rational principles and metaphysics, in contrast to normativeism, which does not allow the discovery of the "specific subjectivity of aesthetics."

The philosopher spoke about the construction of an "aesthetic ontology" that is different from pure aesthetics. Pure aesthetics - *prima aesthica* ("consideration of aesthetics as an object in its ontological forms, analysis of acceptable and existing forms of aesthetic reality") emphasizes the need to overcome the reduction of the object to other (non-aesthetic) forms of aesthetics.

In real life, researchers have promoted ideas such as creating autonomous aesthetics, rejecting reductionist aesthetics, and excluding certain norms or interdisciplinary concepts. Attempts to limit the subordination of pure aesthetics to ontological, epistemological and rational principles are common. Because at one time, it was often observed that the categories of aesthetics were reduced to the concepts of other disciplines (for example, ethics, art history, cultural studies, logic). They tried to express the accepted truth in aesthetics, which is a philosophical science, through the concept of "aesthetic pleasure", to include aesthetic pleasure in pure "aesthetic ontology" as opposed to the utilitarian interpretation of hedonistic ethics. In it, an abstract being through an objective connection with the transcendent and the eternal requires the formation of a separate area of concepts of synthetic knowledge. In particular, it is emphasized that beauty and truth, which are the main central categories of morality and aesthetics, are included in dialectical, ontological relations in the forms of "abstract being" and "reality". Pure aesthetics regards beauty as "the fullness of abstract forms of being", and truth as the fruit of scientific research into reality. "If 'truth' is an existing concept, then 'beauty' is a state of neglect." [2,310].

The above analytical considerations show that morality and aesthetics in the spiritual existence of a person are based on philosophical dualism, which arises as a unit of comparative simultaneous action, emotional, rational cognitive experience.

Because the individual consciousness of a person is a trinity that includes logic (mental-rational), morality and aesthetics. Consequently, a specific subjective aspect of aesthetics is that it has a deep ontological interaction with the sciences of ethics and logic. In our opinion, there is no need to put the "Great Wall of China" between the identification of these two fronts, but it is necessary to study more deeply the interaction of these two fronts. Failure to grasp the true meaning of ethics, aesthetics and logic threatens our knowledge of the subject. This leads to misinterpretation of the true qualities of goodness and beauty, to immorality, and then to "pure" aesthetics.

Sometimes one of the components of the concepts of goodness, justice, beauty, which are eternal truths found in social life, takes precedence, and the rest of the concepts play a dominant role

as complementary to the content, meaningful. Thus, the central concept of religious faith is the understanding of good and truth as a true religious teaching. In logical cognition, science is viewed as faith, and in human life - as a creator. In accordance with the requirements of rationalism, truth in science was closer to the true criterion of reasoning and theory, good - to utility and purposefulness (utilitarianism), and beauty - to a straightforward structure, smoothing out natural differences and forming geometry. Consequently, our rational knowledge could incorporate our epistemic knowledge of truth, goodness, and beauty into ethical and aesthetic sciences, while limiting their development. As long as the human heart is above knowledge and experience at a theoretical level, it must understand beauty on the basis of moral balance and truth, without disturbing the harmony of reality.

At present, the concentration of beauty in the field of art and sports, its liberation from "utilitarian objects and various goals and interests" brings art closer to a type that combines a state of pleasure, relaxation, excitement, relaxation. "Beauty in art is like truth in science. This is the relationship between content and form, harmony of one with the other, which allows us to touch the invisible depths of life and other worlds." [3,8-9]. Art is an object of aesthetic research, which harmoniously analyzes current issues of ethics and aesthetics. A work of art reflects positive and negative qualities through an image, a plot, a logical construction of an artistic composition decorates the work, gradually reflects aesthetic categories in the mind of the reader. This means that "a work of art studied in the field of art will at the same time be studied from an ethical point of view. However, such closeness does not mean semantic accuracy". [4,81].

The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle was right when he said that goodness manifests itself only in action, and beauty also manifests itself in inaction. Morality and aesthetics are manifested in the form of content and form, community and specificity, disproportion and harmony, and are studied as a dialectical, synergistic phenomenon in the spheres of life. [5,326].

In this part of our research, we aimed to conduct a conceptual analysis of the synthesis of ethics and aesthetics. At the same time, first of all, ethical and aesthetic sciences have a separate object of study, which led to the neglect of some subtle units of unity. Secondly, morality and aesthetics are, first of all, a kind of understanding of the spiritual world of a person, from an ontological, epistemological point of view, the study of two inseparable aspects of the studied object in one space and time, thirdly, keep in mind that these two inseparable concepts simultaneously explore the spiritual existence of a person, the movement and inaction of a being, fourthly, it is emphasized that in the spiritual world of the individual, aesthetics is inevitably associated with ethics and that aesthetization or the inverse relationship of the spiritual and moral existence of the individual remains an object of research in these areas of science.

In general, based on the above considerations, the synthesis of ethics and aesthetics and their analysis in three concepts leads to the following conclusions:

Firstly, in the sense of beauty, which has a moral constant, it approaches the content not only by virtue, but also by "truth-justice." Beauty is created by the labor and thinking of people - it manifests itself in the form of the reality of people, and beauty that does not depend on a person is distinguished by the nature of space and time; secondly, the semantic integration of the disciplines of ethics and aesthetics, first of all, the analysis of their metaphysical meanings, the unification of these two areas under one goal (some authors say that under one roof) is seen as a solution to ethical, ethical problems in society; thirdly, the aesthetics of morality, or the morality of aesthetics, indicates its opposite. He defines the border between good and evil and explains what is beauty and what is not. In the theory of personal education, the individual gives knowledge about the normative polar aspects of didactics as the antipode of virtues and vices; fourthly, there are authors who interpret morality and aesthetics mainly as indivisible and indivisible spheres, such as the concepts of goodness and beauty, as well as those who defend their pure ontology, the separation of objects. The unification of their views, their adaptation to the principles of the methodology of logical knowledge is a topical issue; Fifthly, the aesthetics of morality, the tendency to moralize aesthetics, is becoming more and more relevant for our time. The authors (M.S.Kagan, L.A. Zags, N.V. Golik, V. Nabokov, M. Nurmatova, T. Makhmudov, etc.) claim that the harmony of moral and aesthetic values, the effectiveness of their joint study, they emphasize the need to keep the current aesthetics under moral

control, that is, to preserve the moral aesthetics, to maintain the symmetry of the connection between these axiological "Siamese twins".

The globalization of the twentieth century has led to national-ethnic, social, religious conflicts. Conflicts, social-class conflicts, and in some ideological contexts the areas of aesthetics and ethics continued to remain antagonistic, even recognizing them as opposing areas. Now their approach is assessed in an incomprehensible way, as if combining religious knowledge with the achievements of science. The interpretation of the German classical philosopher I. Kant in this regard can have a common denominator for all humanistic, democratic trends and bring universal possibilities to the philosophical thinking of the 21st century. At present, the tendencies for the synthesis of these two concepts, namely, morality and aesthetics, can be observed in Russian and European schools of thought in the form "Virtue and Truth: Classical and Non-Classical Regulators". They devote a discussion to one of the eternal themes of philosophy - the relationship between truth and good. It analyzes the ethical and epistemological aspects of the interpretation of truth and good in the history of philosophy, and focuses on the problem of disagreement between truth and good, which leads to the gap between ethics, epistemology and the axiology of science. An important breakthrough in the history of philosophy is that "the main vector in the interpretation of the relationship between truth and good is the disagreement between the two forms of debate, ethical and cognitive discourses. This disagreement ultimately led to a split between ethics and epistemology, to the idea of value neutrality of scientific truth, and to the fact that the criteria for true knowledge were not placed in ethical discourse. There is another interpretation - moral and epistemological discussions and the search for the unity of good and truth." [6,3].

Thoughts and views on the synthesis of morality and aesthetics today have led to diversity. They provide a detailed explanation of the reality of three units (goodness, truth and beauty), and the unity (inseparability) of these concepts determines the boundaries of the methodological and ontological connection between them. The three kingdoms originally established in the writings of the ancient Greeks: truth, goodness and beauty acquired methodological significance. These early views, expressed as metaphysics, are also present in the new philosophy of our day. "They have no basis either in the Bible or in church narratives, and therefore they are not protected from various revolutions, annexations and changes of borders. There were times when the three dimensions of this hierarchy of the ideal universe seemed arbitrary to us. Why should there be three kingdoms, not four, five or two. This is why there are so many attempts to reconsider." [7,321].

G. P Fedotov, based on the idea of "unconnected-integral" unity of truth, goodness and beauty, explained the state of "non-union" in order to avoid false substitution and interference. There is a mutual attraction and disintegration between these three, since the supreme kingdoms are not at all close to each other. But this cannot be the basis for the final denial of synthesis and unity. To leave the unity of the trinity, especially the importance of unity, it is necessary to have a clear understanding of the qualitative stratification of these concepts and the logical boundaries between them.

In the field of ethics and aesthetics, there is a philosophical methodology that studies the foundations of the emotionally rational, valuable world of humanity in the field of ethics and aesthetics. Human cognition and its value aspects are intertwined in epistemology. We know this from the existence of research areas such as ethics, aesthetics, cognitive theory, and values. It should not be forgotten that moral laws in society are universal, the laws of philosophical knowledge are universal, the individuality of aesthetic pleasure. On the other hand, "ethics and aesthetics are sisters, since they deal with the world of necessity, and knowledge with the world of existence. There are also differences: art and morality build their own world, and science finds it." [7,323].

In general, the above analysis recognizes the unity of ethics and aesthetics, the quality of the system of important legal ties. Opposition of aesthetics to ethics, or vice versa, means that a particular social system is experiencing an escalation of global problems, which indicates a sharp change, a weakening. The period of the convergence of ethics and aesthetics, the emphasis on the similarity and unity between them, the period when the human heart realizes the tendency towards the opposite, is the period of ascent. Through the structural analysis of moral and aesthetic consciousness, researchers can see an attempt to build a dialectical connection between ethics and the science of aesthetics, show

the true complexity and contradictions of these relationships, limit their framework and determine their true space.

There are also supporters of the idea of a synthetic understanding of high spiritual values, primarily for understanding the ideal (A.V. Guliga) and combining knowledge with practice in the context of its achievement. "Truth is not only knowledge, it seeks to embody the reality of the world built in accordance with this knowledge. In this case, knowledge is combined with practice, which is an active transformer of the world and man. Thus, he strives to be similar to reality, goodness and beauty." [8,72]. Consequently, the concepts of truth, goodness and beauty are ideal in nature and are embodied in the form of three images of the ideal in a layer of high spiritual value of a person. Can the subject and object of ethical and aesthetic sciences fully realize that this ideal fully embraces human spirituality? Questions arise naturally. These are questions that modern researchers should pay close attention to.

According to the views that have developed in the history of aesthetics as a "history of synthetic spirituality" (KG Isupov), the subject of aesthetics is "an emotional person," that is, a "mentally unhappy being". [9,9] In this synthetic analysis, human aesthetics is interpreted as "moral self-organization." The anthropological structure of man exists in its "inseparable" unity with other, similar, adjacent, different facets. According to another source, ethics and aesthetics in it, a moral dispute introduces a person as homo aesthetikos (A.E. Zimbuli) in the debate. The deep unity of ethics and aesthetics is embodied in the meaning of the word Aesthetikos. "A person who feels this can be proud, ashamed, sympathetic, sad, flattering, jealous, afraid, jealous." [10,69]. From this it follows that man himself, by his very nature, is a creation of aesthetic nature. His feelings and activities are studied only in directions. The primary general subject area of ethics and aesthetics is in the consciousness of a person as a single whole - a syncretic unit in which there is no analytical delineation of morality, aesthetics, epistemology. Man is a being of a moral and aesthetic nature who is afflicted and angry, hated and respected, afraid of the truth and unable to feel.

The unity of morality and aesthetics, the union of two indivisible forces of the human mind are reflected in research. In the human mind, the study of two closely related forms, emotional states, is divided into ethical and aesthetic: "Isn't the moral state aesthetic, or vice versa: the aesthetic state is similar to the moral state?" - the question arises. The connection between morality and aesthetics is very clear: "The aesthetic state is more productive, more clearly, more clearly reflects the moral state." [11,30]. Fiction provides an aesthetic description of the subtleties of human creativity. In fiction, the poetic process, in the dramatic process, the emotional experiences of a poet or writer are manifested on the basis of high moral rules, on the basis of great elegance. "Aesthetic aesthetics itself is a primary synthetic act" [12,30].

In general, modern researchers have a more classical approach to problems. Studying the concept of reality, researchers approach three units. Truth and goodness reflect a higher, divine view of the world. "Impressions of truth are the basis of a rational approach to life, the idea of good is based on morality, and the idea of beauty is based on aesthetics." [13,623].

Many researchers have considered the whole nature of truth in relation to goodness and beauty. As a result of the interdependence of morality and aesthetics in the spiritual existence of a person, various ideas and views have arisen in scientific research. Ontological, epistemological and axiological approaches to the problem have been formed, most of which concern the question of whether human consciousness and spirituality are inseparable in culture. It is emphasized that a common view from a metaphysical point of view on the unity and uniqueness of morality and aesthetics with modern views reflects the idea of truth, goodness, beauty for a person in the spiritual world of a person.

CONCLUSION

From studies of the synthesis of morality and aesthetics in human consciousness, the following conclusions can be drawn:

firstly, in the spiritual and spiritual structure of the individual, the moral and aesthetic has inseparable and integral parts, the study of which separately gives only a one-sided solution to the problem;

secondly, the study of the content and criteria of good, beauty and truth, the definition, separation, unification of their place in the spiritual culture of the individual has become a valuable eternal movement of mankind;

thirdly, modern researchers focus on the classical view of the fundamental concepts of truth, goodness and beauty, which form the basis of any process of studying the values of being and culture;

fourthly, morality and aesthetics are attributes of the spiritual world of the individual, reflecting two inseparable aspects of the studied object in space and time from an ontological, epistemological point of view;

Fifthly, the inseparability of individual consciousness can be a positive factor in solving today's ethical, environmental problems, reflecting the first ontological state of human spirituality. A logical solution to global, local problems, a way to overcome the escalation of ethical problems - the unification of the content of morality and aesthetics in the consciousness of the individual;

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ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ
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